

INTEGRATING YOUTUBE STORYTELLING VIDEOS IN A COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study discusses the application of YouTube which is integrated into the Communicative Language Approach for Young Learner English learning. The ability to communicate is one of the demands in learning a foreign language. An elementary school teacher at an elementary school held a program so that her students could do storytelling. The program applies Youtube Integration to the CLT approach. The main purpose of this research is to focus on investigating how the teacher applies the CLT approach using YouTube and find out its benefits. Qualitative research design was used in this research. The instruments used were observation and semi-structured interviews. data were grouped, analyzed and described. Thus, the findings from this study are teachers using YouTube in the early stages of learning and at the end of the program. The learning steps and objectives are in accordance with the Communicative Approach principles. Furthermore, several benefits were also found such as making learning fun, exposing students, increasing students' pronunciation, vocabulary and confidence in communicating.

KEYWORDS

YouTube, Communicative Approach, Young Learner, Speaking, Storytelling

INTRODUCTION

In teaching and learning activities, teachers may face some difficulties when teaching young learners. They feel insufficient in understanding the knowledge, understanding the material, and rarely have some practice (Copland et al., 2014). In addition, teachers will also find challenges related to young learners because of their character. They have to be patient with it. Of course, there are differences between young learners when compared to others. Slattery & Willis, (2001) states various student characters including young people have good hearing and experience, get new information by playing and doing things, have a great interest in sound, and when they are old enough they like to think about something, know what something is whether it's real or not, plan something, work in a team, and have a good sense of responsibility. Therefore, teachers are required to have a specific strategy for teaching language to young learners.

Current technological developments are able to support English teaching and learning activities for young learners. Sun et al., (2017) also supports that the use of technology can help improve young learners' speaking skills. One of the technologies that is easy to access and used as a learning medium for young learners is YouTube (Oktrianur, 2022). On YouTube there are various videos that teachers can use. Integration and implementation of technology in schools supports learning using mobile device technology by teachers (Crompton et al., 2016). However, in reality in Indonesia, not all teachers are literate in technology, especially in sub urban and rural areas. This is also supported by research on the level of content technology knowledge

and teacher pedagogy (TPACK), the results of which are still low (Taopan, 2020). In fact, to create effective learning, creative and innovative teachers are needed (Setiawan et al., 2019).

In Indonesia, the Merdeka Curriculum which implemented in 2022, English learning for elementary schools is raised again. One of the goals of the English language mentioned in the independent Curriculum document is to develop communicative competence in English with various multimodal texts (oral, written, visual and audiovisual). To achieve this goal, teachers are free to choose learning methods that suit the needs of their students. One method that can be used is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). The communicative approach is basically a set of principles about the purpose of teaching language, how learners learn language, the types of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teacher and learner in the classroom (Richards, 2006). The goals of the approach itself is to know the use of language both in terms of function, setting and interlocutor, and to be able to carry out conversations that involve grammar and fluency.

One of the teachers at an elementary school in a suburban area held a storytelling program. She integrates YouTube Storytelling videos into Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) learning activities for 5th grade elementary school students. The purpose of this activity is to learn English while telling stories. In addition, students can also get to know about narrative texts and cultures from various countries.

Several previous studies on the use of YouTube on English language teaching have been carried out. The existence of the Covid 19 era pandemic and new normal era also increased the use of YouTube as an interactive media and elicited good responses from students (Sirait et al., 2021; Syafiq et al., 2021). Sari & Iswahyuni, (2019), in Indonesia setting, conducted research on the use of YouTube video projects for teaching speaking and found that YouTube video projects were the preferred media based on the responses of 104 students stating they preferred working on YouTube video projects over other speaking activities such as telling stories, oral presentations, and speeches. Alobaid, (2020) conducted research on the influence of YouTube on writing and the results showed that there were statistically significant differences in several aspects but not in the aspects of students' writing fluency; basically, accuracy and organization of ideas as a qualitative dimension of fluency increase after actual exposure to YouTube. Gracella & Rahman Nur, (2020) also investigated students' perceptions of YouTube use, and the findings revealed that students were able to improve their English skills, and it was very easy to access in almost every student gadget to assist and motivate them to learn English, but students only felt difficulty if there was a poor internet connection. The use of YouTube for young learners, it has been previously studied but using YouTube kids animation and its effect on students vocabulary (Oktrianur, 2022). However, there is still a lack of research on the use of YouTube storytelling in communicative language teaching activities. Therefore, this research focuses on the use of YouTube in a Communicative language teaching approach for elementary school students to do storytelling.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teaching English to Young Learners

Young learners are those who are still in language development and are around 7-12 years old. Young learners are candidates for any language learning agency, including English. Wallin and

Cheevakumjorn (2020) assert that the younger children learn a language, the faster they immerse the language in their language acquisition. Piaget's theory, (1967); Vygotsky, (1962); & Bruner, (1996) shows the inevitable link between cognitive and language development of children, Piaget's theory reconfirms that all types of teaching can be effective only if the child is able to assimilate what is being said and complete, a concept he refers to as " learning readiness". Furthermore, Shin and Crandall (2014) stated that there are four reasons for starting language learning earlier, namely; the value of increased time, the possibility of better pronunciation and fluency, the possibility of greater global awareness and intercultural competence, and the value of bilingualism.

The English for Young Learner program must be carried out as soon as possible with the most appropriate lesson plans. Teaching English to young learners can either help or risk the student. It is good if the teacher can facilitate learning and let students bring their motivation and desire to comprehend into learning language; thus, the teacher could assist students in overcoming their obstacles (Prayatni, 2019). Since 2004, Indonesia has been teaching English to young learners as a supplementary course in elementary schools. Furthermore, English is taught for a variety of inputs with no rules instructing teachers to teach. Basically, in young English classes, the teacher must utilize a variety of methods to interest students' enthusiasm for learning; they must introduce the role of language as a medium of communication and make them ready to use it (Nufus, 2019). According to Nikolov and Curtain as cited by Shin and Crandall (2014) there are characteristics of young learner programs such as: focusing on meaning, integrating language teaching with the mainstream curriculum, using task-based and content-based approaches, providing a pleasant atmosphere in class and increasing the likelihood of success student. In addition, teachers must be able to foster student independence with realistic expectations and assessments, as well as provide continuity between elementary and secondary school programs.

Youtube Storytelling Videos

Storytelling used to be a joyful activity. Storytelling is also related to narrative text, which tells about fairy tales and legends. From there students can learn about culture. People's culture and memories includes fairy tales, mythology, and historical stories (Dusi et al., 2017). We now live in a world where social media has altered human interactions through various communication patterns. These stories have expanded beyond digital platforms, where they are presently constructing alternate fictional universes consisting of characters, places, and various realities. Youtube is one platform that offers storytelling videos, which the storytelling has extended to music, where cover videos have high relevance (Vizcaíno-Verdú et al., 2021).

YouTube is an online platform that provides many videos that can be freely accessed by people using the internet who live in this modern era. With over 2 billion viewers, YouTube is the largest online video digital channel, and over a billion hours of Youtube videos are seen every day, mainly among younger generations (Duffett, 2020). A study by Yanto & Nugraha (2018), explains that watching YouTube videos can be beneficial for students. Their study is also in line with Susanti et al. (2022), they agree that the use of video as a learning medium will be beneficial because it can develop skills and motivate students as long as it is used correctly. The use of YouTube in everyday life as the modern generation has become familiar. Therefore, students will feel very happy and relaxed when they see video clips so that they can gain an easier understanding (Oktrianur, 2022).

Communicative Language Teaching Approach

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) was introduced in the last quarter of the 20th century when large populations of people migrated to Europe and the United States from various parts of the world primarily for employment or permanent residence. The large influx of foreign workers has put pressure on educators to devise new teaching methods that can help familiarize them with the target language so that they can communicate comfortably with people in their social or professional environment. CLT is welcomed as a useful teaching approach for ELT as it can target all four skills namely, listening, speaking, reading and writing foreign languages through meaningful interactions with an emphasis on communication and meaning. In fact, CLT is seen as an effective means of knowledge transmission through flexible communication (Raja et al., 2017).

Hymes, (1996) believes that communicative competence can be defined in four categories, namely:

- Language skills: knowledge of language symbols such as syntax, sounds, word formation rules, vocabulary, etc.
- Social language skills-the ability to apply the four skills in everyday living settings.
- Textual competence: where speakers can handle grammatical forms and context into meaningful structures in spoken and written formats and text unity can be resolved by language convergence and semantic coherence.
- Strategic competence: skills to increase the effectiveness of communication or to avoid possible mistakes, both in the verbal and nonverbal fields.

With CLT began a movement away from traditional lesson formats where the focus was on mastery of different items of grammar and practice through controlled activities such as memorization of dialogs and drills, and toward the use of pair work activities, role plays, group work activities and project work. The types of classroom activities proposed in CLT also imply new roles in the classroom for teachers and students. Learners must now participate in classroom activities that are based on cooperative rather than individualistic approaches to learning. Students should be comfortable with listening to their peers on group work or pair work assignments, rather than relying on the teacher as a model. They are expected to take a greater degree of responsibility for their own learning. And the teacher now has to act as a facilitator and monitor.

Today, CLT can be seen as indicative of a core set of principles about language learning and teaching, assumptions that can be applied in different ways and which address different aspects of the teaching and learning process (Richards, 2006). Types of class activities that can be used to implement a communicative approach, such as group work, assignment work, and information gap activities.

RESEARCH METHODS

The design of this research is descriptive qualitative which describes data about certain phenomena. Qualitative research is an exploration of individual understanding of certain social problems (Creswell, 2012). The participant of this study was a 5th grade teacher in a private

elementary school in a sub-urban area who implemented a storytelling program using YouTube and a communicative language teaching approach.

Data from this study were collected from classroom observations and in-depth interviews. Through observation, researchers collect data related to how the teacher conducts the storytelling program. Then interviews were conducted to get deeper information (Creswell, 2012) and find out the benefits and obstacles of implementing YouTube video storytelling in the CLT approach and student output. Researchers then analyzed the collected data using categorization and coding to facilitate qualitative data analysis (Ary, D. et. al, 2009).

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Implementation of YouTube Storytelling videos

The duration of the Storytelling program is 60 minutes or one hour every week, on Thursdays. There have been several stages in the CLT method integrated with YouTube Storytelling such as, pre-teaching activities, whilst teaching activities and post teaching activities.

Pre-teaching activities

The teacher introduces narrative text, what narrative text is, its function, and the form of good narrative. The teacher explains that narrative text is a type of text that tells a series of events in a chronological system or is interconnected. Narrative texts are generally imaginative, aka not real or in the form of the imagination of the author. Then, the teacher also mentions examples of narrative text, which can be in the form of legends, myths, and fairy tales. Stories from narrative text usually contain a moral message. A good narrative is one whose structure and chronology are correct and the language is understandable. After students understand about narrative text, they are given a form to fill in later when the lesson takes place.

Whilst teaching activities

When the lesson took place, the teacher played two short story videos alternately. The video was taken from YouTube where the delivery is a form of storytelling. Video duration is around 3-5 minutes. While watching the video, students can fill out the previously distributed form regarding their opinion on the story that has been played. Students watched the video carefully and enthusiastically filled out the forms. After that, the teacher asks students to choose one of the stories from the video that has been played. The selected story is their favorite story. Students then retell in their own language what they have seen and give their opinion. The words used by students are still very simple. Occasionally students are assisted by the teacher for certain vocabulary. They told stories and opinions one by one in turn. Students listen when other students explain and sometimes give some comment.

Post teaching activities

Students write down messages from the stories they have witnessed. Then students are given a form which they use to create their own story. At the end of the lesson, the teacher reflects again on what has been learned that day. Then students convey the moral message of the story they have witnessed before. Furthermore, students were asked to then create their own stories and write them down in a form that had been provided by the teacher. The form has been adapted to the narrative text structure and is carried out in stages every week. This is done, because in communicating not only orally but also in written. Thus, it is hoped that the objectives of the

communicative approach which includes fluency and accuracy will be achieved. Students not only learn to speak but also know about structure and grammar.

The output of this activity is that students can apply some of the new vocabulary they get from the video. Students understand several pronunciations that they have been saying wrong all this time. Students are also able to converse briefly in English and use appropriate intonation and expressions. At the end of the semester, students are able to create and tell their own storytelling which can also be uploaded on YouTube

From the whole learning process, the following are the responses from the students. Even though they did not fully understand English, the students' responses were quite positive. Students can understand the plot of the story by watching video short stories. Students also seem to enjoy learning English more by watching movies. Evidenced by their enthusiasm to answer questions and express their opinions.

The results above show that YouTube Storytelling is used by teachers as an interesting medium. This is in line with previous research that YouTube is a technology that is easy to use for learning media, especially children (Oktrianur, 2022). Then this is also in line with previous research which stated that Youtube videos are considered as effective learning media, but technology alone is not enough, methods and teacher guidance are needed to bring benefits to students, especially young learners (Yaacob et al., 2021). From observations in class, we can see that the approach used by the teacher is the Communicative Language Teaching Approach. The main principles of communicative language teaching are mechanical, meaningful, and communicative practices, which are applied in the classroom (Richards, 2006). From the teaching process applied by the teacher above, it has included these components which are the basis of CLT. The teacher provides YouTube storytelling videos as a trigger so that students are more enthusiastic in communicating, and share their ideas. Then at the end of the lesson, the teacher also uses YouTube as a media for students to convey their storytelling.

The benefits of Integrating YouTube Storytelling video

From the results of interviews with teachers who run this program, we get results related to the benefits obtained from using YouTube Storytelling in the Communicative Language Teaching approach.

Fun Learning

The first benefit felt in class is that the teacher succeeded in creating fun learning.

"Students can learn English more fun, they are more enthusiastic when I play a video"

From the teacher's statement, we can see that learning using YouTube videos can be fun learning.

Student Exposure

The second benefit of using YouTube videos in the CLT approach is as exposure for students to speak English. According to the teacher, by using YouTube, students can understand English and it's like listening to native speaker's speech.

"Using YouTube videos in class, it's like students are learning directly from native speakers without the need to bring in the person directly."

Pronunciation

The third benefit is the effect on student pronunciation. The teacher stated that the students' pronunciation was better because they got examples from YouTube.

"By watching the YouTube videos that are played, students know how to pronounce English correctly and correctly".

The use of YouTube can help teachers to provide examples of correct pronunciation, so that in speaking students can pronounce the correct pronunciation. This is of course also in line with the goals of CLT.

Vocabularies

The fourth benefit is an increase in vocabulary by students, which according to the teacher's statement, can be seen from the progress of students in understanding stories every week.

"Students' vocabulary has also increased, this can be seen from their understanding of stories and the use of words used when expressing opinions."

Student self-confidence

The next benefit is the increased confidence of students to speak.

"The use of YouTube storytelling can provide insight for students so they are able to be more confident in speaking because they understand what is being discussed."

Students who previously did not dare to speak English because they did not know what to talk about, became brave and confident because they know the topic from the YouTube video they have watched.

From the results described above, this is similar to some previous research on YouTube videos for young learners. YouTube is regarded as an additional method for enhancing students' speaking skills. By watching YouTube-based videos, students are supposed to gain ideas for speaking, allowing them to develop communication performances that are imitative, intensive, responsive, intensive, interactive, and broad (Syafiq et al., 2021). Previous research has also indicated that students become enthused about using movies on YouTube in class because they feel pleased, motivated, and the class environment becomes enjoyable; students are involved in learning via technology, and they believe that using technology to support the learning process is very beneficial (Hariyono, 2020). Furthermore, using YouTube videos in class allows students to see examples of pronunciation, giving them the opportunity to better pronunciation (Syafiq et al., 2021). Then, young learner interact with the teacher and other students, are eager to make comments, and using YouTube videos helps students understand vocabulary (Hariyono, 2020). Other previous studies also stated that young learner get new vocabulary from watching videos from YouTube (Arianti et al., 2018; Oktrianur, 2022; Syafiq et al., 2021). From this study it is also stated that Youtube videos collaborated with the CLT method can increase students' self-confidence to speak, these results are still rarely found in previous studies.

We do not cover obstacles in this paper since, according to the teacher, there are no big problem for the teacher. According to the teacher, the implementation has been going according to plan. The only thing that remains challenging is changing students' perspectives so that they love studying English, but this issue may be handled progressively using this program.

CONCLUSION

Finally, programs that include YouTube into a communicative approach to teaching English to young learners are advantageous. It is used in pre-teaching activities, Whilst teaching activities, and post-teaching activities. The teacher distributes a form before showing a YouTube video to the students. Students then provide their thoughts upon that video. The teacher also provides a form for students to fill out in order to write their own narrative stories. Students learn not only how to speak, but also about structure and grammar. They are required to be able to communicate not only orally but also in written. Students are able to share their narrative at the end of the lesson and publish it to YouTube. The students' reaction was very enthusiastic. Students are found to like learning English more when they watch videos. The components that form the foundation of CLT are included in the instructional technique used by the teacher above. Furthermore, various advantages were discovered, such as making learning more enjoyable, exposing students, and improving students' pronunciation, vocabulary, and communication confidence. Then for obstacles not found to be such a big problem.

Recommendation for Practice

For further research, we recommend that more participants be studied. In addition, it is also advisable to look for media related to other technologies and be integrated with a learning method. This is necessary to increase the effectiveness of learning English in the classroom.

REFERENCES

- Alobaid, A. (2020). Smart multimedia learning of ICT: role and impact on language learners' writing fluency— YouTube online English learning resources as an example. *Smart Learning Environments*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-020-00134-7>
- Arianti, A., Nurnaningsih, M., & Pratiwi, V. (2018). *A Media For Teaching Speaking Using Youtube Video*. 175(Icase), 71–73. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icase-18.2018.19>
- Ary, Donald.et. al. *Introduction to Research in Education Eighth Edition*. (Canada: Cengage Learning, 2009)
- Copland, F., Garton, S., & Burns, A. (2014). Challenges in Teaching English to Young Learners: Global Perspectives and Local Realities. *TESOL Quarterly*, 48(4), 738–762. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.148>
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research (4th ed.)*. Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Crompton, H., Olszewski, B., & Bielefeldt, T. (2016). The mobile learning training needs of educators in technology-enabled environments. *Professional Development in Education*, 42(3), 482–501. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2014.1001033>
- Duffett, R. (2020). The youtube marketing communication effect on cognitive, affective and behavioural attitudes among generation Z consumers. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12125075>
- Dusi, N.; Ferretti, I.; Furini, M. A transmedia storytelling system to transform recorded film memories into visual history. *Entertain. Comput.* 2017, 21, 65–75
- Gracella, J., & Rahman Nur, D. (2020). Students' Perception of English Learning through YouTube Application. *Borneo Educational Journal (Borju)*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.24903/bej.v2i1.623>

- Hariyono, T. C. (2020). TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNER USING VIDEO ON YOUTUBE AT ENGLISH COURSE. *Language Research Society*, 1(1).
<https://doi.org/10.33021/lrs.v1i1.1038>
- Hymes, D. (1996). *Ethnography, linguistics, narrative inequality: Toward an understanding of voice*. London, UK: Taylor & Francis
- Nufus, T. Z. (2019). Teaching English to Young Learners in Indonesia (Pros and Cons). *English Language in Focus (ELIF)*, 1(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.24853/elif.1.1.65-70>
- Oktrianur, H. R. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF KID ANIMATIONS ON YOUTUBE AS LEARNING MEDIA IN TEACHING. *RETAIN (Research on English Language Teaching in Indonesia)*, 10(01), 187–194.
- Prayatni, I. (2019). Teaching English For Young Learners. *Jurnal Ilmiah Profesi Pendidikan*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.29303/jipp.v4i2.90>
- Raja, M. S. H., Qureshi, A. S. A. R., & Albeshier, K. B. (2017). Application of cooperative learning strategies (Cls) for students' focused teaching (sft) in efl class: An experimental study in the summer remedial course for adult learners. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 8(2), 237–252. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0802.05>
- Richards, J. C. (2006). Communicative Language Teaching Paradigm. In *Cambridge University Press* (Vol. 1, Issue 1). <https://www.professorjackrichards.com/wp-content/uploads/Richards-Communicative-Language.pdf>
- Sari, A. B. P., & Iswahyuni, D. (2019). THE STUDENTS' SPEAKING ANXIETY ON THE YOUTUBE VIDEO PROJECT IN EFL LEARNING IN INDONESIA. *Premise: Journal of English Education*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.24127/pj.v8i2.2179>
- Setiawan, A., Munir, A., & Suhartono, S. (2019). Creative Teachers in Teaching Speaking Performance. *Pedagogy: Journal of English Language Teaching*, 7(2), 75.
<https://doi.org/10.32332/pedagogy.v7i2.1670>
- Shin, J., & Crandall, J. (2014). *Teaching Young Learners English: From Theory to Practice*. Singapore: Heinle Cengage Learning.
- Sirait, D., Harahap, Y. S., & Handayani, A. T. (2021). THE USE OF YOUTUBE-BASED INTERACTIVE LEARNING MEDIA IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN THE NEW NORMAL ERA. *European Journal of English Language Teaching*, 6(4).
<https://doi.org/10.46827/ejel.v6i4.3703>
- Sun, Z., Lin, C. H., You, J., Shen, H. jiao, Qi, S., & Luo, L. (2017). Improving the English-speaking skills of young learners through mobile social networking. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 30(3–4), 304–324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2017.1308384>
- Susanti, A., Presdyasmara, C., Dewi, F., & Wardani, Y. (2022). Developing Students' English Skill Through Digital Video as Multimodal for Young Learners in Online Learning. *Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Arts and Humanities 2021 (IJCAH 2021)*, 618(January). <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211223.040>
- Syafiq, A. N., Rahmawati, A., Anwari, A., & Oktaviana, T. (2021). Increasing Speaking Skill through YouTube Video as English Learning Material during Online Learning in Pandemic Covid-19. *Elsya: Journal of English Language Studies*, 3(1).
<https://doi.org/10.31849/elsya.v3i1.6206>
- Taopan, L. L. (2020). Tpack Framework: Challenges and Opportunities in Efl Classrooms. *Research and Innovation in Language Learning*, 3(1), 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.33603/rill.v3i1.2763>
- Vizcaíno-Verdú, A., Aguaded, I., & Contreras-Pulido, P. (2021). Understanding transmedia music on youtube through disney storytelling. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(7).

<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073667>

- Wallin, J., & Cheevakumjorn, B. (2020). Learning English as a Second Language: Earlier is Better. *Journal of English Educators Society*, 5(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2264117>
- Yaacob, A., Amir, A. S. A., Mohd Asraf, R., Mohd Yaakob, M. F., & Zain, F. M. (2021). Impact of Youtube and Video Podcast on Listening Comprehension Among Young Learners. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 15(20). <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v15i20.23701>
- Yanto, E. S., & Nugraha, S. I. (2018). Video viewing as a mediation of learning content-based vocabulary: Assisting students in understanding disciplinary vocabulary in context. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 8(2), 316–324. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v8i2.13278>